

APPLYING SPACEVPX MODULAR OPEN SYSTEMS INTERCONNECT CONCEPTS

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Abstract

The VITA-78 SpaceVPX System Specification recently passed American National Standards Institute (ANSI) ballot and is now ready for wide adoption as the MOSA standard for space systems. It inherits the VPX/OpenVPX pedigree and adds single point fault tolerant features ideal for space applications. These features work well for 6U size modules, but the same approach results in an excessive degree of overhead for 3U implementations. Consequently, the VITA 78 Working Group spun off the VITA 78.1, SpaceVPX Lite draft standard this year to address these limitations for 3U modules. This paper aims to accelerate adoption of these standards by describing practical concepts for 3U module implementations using the new SpaceVPX Lite approach. The initial work in this area focuses on interconnects for applications needing minimal size, weight, power and cost.

Background

The ANSI/VITA 78-2015 [1] SpaceVPX System Specification was produced by the VME (Versa-Module-Eurocard) International Trade Association (VITA) 78 Working Group. This working group was initiated as part of the Government-Industry collaborative Next Generation Space Interconnect Standard (NGSIS) [2]. The VITA 78 standard has similar structure as the ANSI/VITA 65-2010 [R2012] OpenVPX™ System Specification [3]. OpenVPX rapidly gained broad adoption for avionics systems after its introduction in 2010. It is based on the VPX standard (Versatile Performance Switching) which is defined by ANSI/VITA 46.0-2007 [4]. The VITA 65 OpenVPX Working Group applied system level rules and topologies using the VPX standard infrastructure to create a VPX based system specification. The VITA 78 SpaceVPX Working Group used a similar methodology to produce a system specification intended for space applications. Figure 1, shows the

covers of the VPX, OpenVPX and SpaceVPX standards and the dates when they became ANSI approved. The VME International Trade Association (VITA) makes all of these standards available on their website.

Figure 1. VPX Progressively Moved Open Hardware Architectures from Avionics to Space

Introduction

Those familiar with OpenVPX will see a lot of similarity to SpaceVPX with the exception of the Space Utility Management Module commonly referred to as the SpaceUM. Another more subtle difference occurs in the concept of a “Controller” module. In OpenVPX, a “system controller” is a payload module capable of driving utility signals REF_CLK±, SYSRESET* and NVMRO. In SpaceVPX, this extends to new utility signals REF_CLK1±, REF_CLK2± (6U modules only) and the system management pins SM(3:0). Another change for SpaceVPX defines SM(3:2) as (SM_STAT*, SM_RESET*) for a more reliable I2C system management interface. Unlike OpenVPX, SpaceVPX System Controllers have their own slot and module profiles. System Controller profiles provide up to four sets of utility signals to interface with up to four SpaceUMs. In 6U form factor, each SpaceUM provides utility signals and power switching to up to eight payload modules yielding a total extensibility to 32 payload modules. However,

in 3U, a SpaceUM provides utility signals to no more than two payload modules. As a result, in 3U, SpaceVPX systems extend out to only six payload modules, with two System Controller modules and four SpaceUM modules, as shown in Figure 2. The limitation for small 3U systems led to the start of the VITA 78.1 SpaceVPXLite working group. This

paper shows the progress to date on this standard, explains its goals and describes some of the methodology behind it. Further information on VPX, OpenVPX and the SpaceVPX standard can be found at www.vita.com. VITA members also have access to the VITA 78.1 SpaceVPXLite Working Group drafts and documents.

Figure 2. SpaceVPX 3U Topologies Need an Onerous Number of Modules to Comply With the Standard

SpaceVPXLite Control Method

In SpaceVPXLite, the 3U System Controller connects the utility signals directly to the payload modules instead of through SpaceUMs. Offloading these signals from the SpaceUM reduces it to just switching power, so the SpaceVPXLite standard designates it as the Power Switch Module (PowerSX). It also enables the PowerSX module to now switch supply power to at least eight payload modules: a vast improvement from two provided by the 3U SpaceUM. Figure 3 shows the SpaceVPXLite System Controller slot profile. To fit eight sets of utility signals on a 3U System Controller, the SpaceVPXLite standard slims down the number of signals required. Signals retained include the SYSRESET*, REF_CLK± and AUX_CLK± since these signals are common to both the SpaceVPX and OpenVPX standards. System integrators can take advantage of this commonality by using OpenVPX payload modules with SpaceVPXLite System Controllers to improve single fault tolerance, or to prototype space hardened SpaceVPXLite payload modules.

New Radially Distributed User Defined Signals

SpaceVPXLite adds user defined signals RAD1_USR, RAD2_USR, RAD3_USR and RAD4_USR. The “RAD” part of the signal name stands for “radial” because these signals radially distribute, point to point, from the System Controller module to the payload modules. The standard assigns them as “user defined” because it does not allocate pins on the payload slot profiles for these signals to land on. Building in a few user defined signals into the standard allows some flexibility to accommodate unforeseen capability and invite creativity in future implementations.

REF_CLK1± and REF_CLK2± Re-Assigned

SpaceVPXLite sacrifices the distribution of REF_CLK1± and REF_CLK2± signals because these pins now have a new purpose. Since SpaceVPXLite places utility signals on the System Controller instead of a SpaceUM, payload modules must now accommodate a redundant set of these signals from a redundant System Controller. REF_CLK1± and REF_CLK2± designated SpaceVPX payload module

pins became the redundant AUX_CLK± and REF_CLK± for SpaceVPXLite. Likewise, the OpenVPX pin MaskableRESET* became the redundant SYSRESET*. In the current SpaceVPX standard, 3U System Controllers do not include

REF_CLK1± and REF_CLK2±, so these pins are left unused on 3U payload modules anyway. SpaceVPXLite now gives them a purpose as redundant AUX_CLK± and REF_CLK±.

Figure 3. SpaceVPXLite System Controller Slot Profiles Provide All Utility Signals Needed to Connect Eight Modules into a System Plus Four User Defined Signals to Accommodate Unique Functions

Assigning User Defined Signals in Profiles

Consistent with the OpenVPX philosophy, module profiles define a set of standard implementations to address how to assign radially distributed user defined pins RADn_USRxx, where the “n” designates signal 1, 2, 3 or 4 and “xx” designates the module it goes to. If the application requires additional clocks where the payload module designates four user defined pins as clocks, then SpaceVPXLite allows the System Controller to connect the SpaceVPX defined REF_CLK1± and REF_CLK2± to these pins. Consequently, SpaceVPXLite now adds SpaceVPX clock functionality formally restricted to only 6U modules.

User Defined Signals to Implement IPMI

As another example, users may choose to implement a radial distribution of the Intelligent

Platform Management Interface (IPMI) [5], with signals IPMB_SCL and IPMB_SDA on two of the four RADn_USR pins. In this case, the SM(1:0) pins connect to IPMBA_SCL and IPMBA_SDA from the primary System Controller, and the SM(3:2) pins connect to IPMBB_SCL and IPMBB_SDA from the secondary System Controller. A system so configured effectively becomes a radial version of OpenVPX using VITA 46.11 System Management.

Direct Access Protocol on SpaceVPXLite

Figure 4 illustrates a SpaceVPXLite topology where the System Controller interfaces with the PowerSX over system management as described in the SpaceVPX base standard as the Direct Access Protocol. The SpaceVPXLite standard offers the opportunity to define a primary and secondary set of SM(3:0) going to the PowerSX module because the module and slot profiles are just now being worked

out in the VITA 78.1 Working Group. For payload modules, however, SpaceVPX Direct Access Protocol cannot connect with a SpaceVPXLite System Controller because it defines only one set of SM(3:0) pins, and it needs two sets for a dual redundant connection. Changing SpaceVPX payload module pinouts after the standard achieves ANSI approval disrupts product development, so the VITA 78.1 Working Group decided to avoid new pin assignments as much as possible. If the final VITA 78.1 standard allows a primary and redundant set of

SM(3:0) on the PowerSX, then SpaceVPXLite System Controllers still command all the on/off power switches to the payload modules just like SpaceVPX using the Direct Access Protocol. Only the location of where the switching occurs differs, namely at the PowerSX instead of on the payload module. If the PowerSX keeps only one set of SM(3:0), then System Control still may use system management, but with the ubiquitous IPMB-A and IPMB-B rather than the Direct Access Protocol.

Figure 4. SpaceVPXLite Topology for Six 3U Payload Modules Requires Two Less Modules than an Equivalent Topology in SpaceVPX; Also Adds User Defined Signals Tailored to Meet Unique Needs

SpaceVPXLite Utility Control Differences

Utility control in SpaceVPXLite differs from SpaceVPX in subtle ways. In SpaceVPX, the System Controller communicates over the system management bus using Direct Access Protocol to each payload module through the SpaceUM. The SpaceUM acts like a switch between the two System Controller's SMB. Over this bus, the System Controller may command the modules to power on or off as well as receive status among other capabilities. However, SpaceVPXLite does not include a mandatory system management interface to payload modules. Instead, it offers options defined through profiles on the radially distributed user defined signals. Providing flexibility in utility control for 3U

enables module suppliers to allocate less board area and logic resources to system management overhead. As shown in Figure 4 and previously mentioned, modules may still implement system management over I2C on the radially distributed user defined pins.

The SpaceVPXLite approach allows System Controllers to connect with ubiquitous open standards such as SPI, UART as well as I2C to payload modules regardless of which pins these services map to on the payload module. In comparison, SpaceVPX constricts utility control to a specific protocol and pins for consistency and assured interoperability between compliant modules.

Utility Signal Cross-Strapping

Cross-strapping of utility signals became a necessary element of SpaceVPXLite on account of moving them off the SpaceUM to make room for more power supply pins and support up to eight payload modules. Each payload module must receive two sets of SYSRESET*, AUX_CLK± and REF_CLK±, but no OpenVPX or SpaceVPX designated pins exist to accommodate the redundant set. As a result, the SpaceVPXLite standard needs to repurpose existing pins. The easiest choice for a redundant SYSRESET* is MaskableReset*. SpaceVPXLite may use this signal unmodified from OpenVPX because the OpenVPX standard includes a permission to allow using it as another SYSRESET*:

“Permission 3.4.3-1: A Plug-In Module or RTM

deployed in an OpenVPX backplane may include a second reset input from the backplane as a complement to the SYSRESET* input.” OpenVPX provides no such accommodations for secondary AUX_CLK± and REF_CLK±, but SpaceVPX comes close. It assigns REF_CLK1± and REF_CLK2± on payload module user defined OpenVPX P1 pins. SpaceVPX allows user defined tailoring of both of these clocks. To use them effectively as secondary AUX_CLK± and REF_CLK±, respectively, the SpaceVPXLite standard will need to include a rule so stating to convey to module suppliers the need to build-in switch-over capability. Figures 5 and 6 show the “primary and secondary” connections between System Controller modules and payload modules.

Figure 5. SpaceVPXLite Primary Utility Signal Connections from the System Controller Connect to Payload Modules on Pins Common with ANSI/VITA 65 OpenVPX

Figure 6. SpaceVPXLite Secondary Utility Signal Connections to Payload Modules Rely on Redefining SpaceVPX REF_CLK1± and REF_CLK2± as Secondary AUX_CLK± and REF_CLK±

SpaceVPXLite Utility Signal Switchover

The SpaceVPXLite standard does not put into place a mechanism to determine which utility clocks and reset to listen to. If implementations place the redundant System Controller as always cold spared, then it does not matter. The payload module simply does an OR-ing of the primary and secondary inputs. If the implementation allows both switched on, then the payload modules must rely on the System Controllers to correctly arbitrate control. If an error occurs where both System Controllers take control, due to an error caused by space single event effects for example, then the payload modules must rely on upstream processes to identify the rogue System Controller and shut it down. In SpaceVPX, the secondary System Controller's signals cannot interfere with the primary System Controller's signals because the SpaceUM physically switches it out. But if the primary System Controller fails, then the upstream controller of the SYS_CON_SEL[5:0]

signals must discover the failure and switch to the active System Controller. Until the switchover happens, SpaceVPX payload modules have no control and potentially no clock either. SpaceVPXLite on the other hand offers payload modules the opportunity to detect when the primary controller fails to automatically switch over to the redundant controller.

Redundant Power Supply Switching

Both SpaceVPXLite and SpaceVPX perform redundant power supply switching in one or more dedicated modules. For SpaceVPX, the SpaceUM switches between primary and redundant power supplies under external control as commanded through discrete input signals. SpaceVPXLite does the same except it now uses a module called the PowerSX because it only does power switching where the SpaceUM switches utility signals as well.

Both of these standards include the capability to switch power to individual 3U slots.

SpaceVPX Power Supply Switching

In SpaceVPX, the System Controller may switch a payload module on/off over the system management bus using the Direct Access Protocol over IPMB-A on SM(1:0) with SM_STAT and SM_RESET on SM(3:2). The SM(3:0) routes from each System Controller to the SpaceUM where it switches to the selected System Controller before getting routed out to the payload modules.

SpaceVPXLite Power Supply Switching

SpaceVPXLite permits several methods of payload module power switching depending on the capabilities provided by the System Controller and PowerSX.

IPMI Direct to Payload Modules

If the System Controllers support designating two of the RADn_USR signals on the P2 connector as SM(1:0), then they can command payload power switching by direct connection to the payload module using this IPMB. No power switching at the

PowerSX required. In this case, SM(1:0) from one System Controller maps to SM(1:0) on the Payload module and SM(1:0) of the other System Controller routes to SM(3:2) of the Payload Module. This resembles OpenVPX which assigns IPMB-A to SM(3:2) and IPMB-B to SM(1:0). Systems so configured use the PowerSX as a means to switch between primary and secondary input power sources only.

IPMI to PowerSX from System Controller P0

A SpaceVPXLite System Controller provides up to eight utility plane interfaces to eight modules on its P2 connector, but it also has one more utility interface on its P0 connector. In OpenVPX, the SM(3:0) pins on Chassis Manager slots connect with IPMB-A and IPMB-B. SpaceVPXLite leaves these pins available for a similar function, but as a point to point system management interface rather than a multi-drop one. These signals connect the PowerSX to the System Controller as shown in Figure 7. In this case, IPMBA on SM(3:2) goes to one PowerSX and IPMBB on SM(1:0) goes to the other PowerSX. Hence, the SpaceVPXLite System Controller connects with eight payload modules in addition to two PowerSX modules.

Figure 7. Eight Payload Modules Deploy in SpaceVPXLite with only Two PowerSX Modules and Two System Controller Modules; System Management Bus Used for PowerSX Controls

SpaceVPX Lite Interoperability with OpenVPX

The VITA 78.1 SpaceVPX Lite standard is in Working Group draft form as of the writing of this paper, but the Working Group intends to preserve interoperability with OpenVPX modules to the greatest extent practical. A SpaceVPX Lite System Controller may communicate directly with OpenVPX payload modules over a radial distribution of the system management bus from an on-board Chassis Manager as described above. Table 1 shows the OpenVPX compatible SpaceVPX Lite System Controller module profile. When applied to all eight 2-wafers sets of the utility management plane defined on the System Controller P2 connector, we achieve OpenVPX compatibility with the exception of dual redundancy support. Currently, no OpenVPX payload slot profile exists that provides pins for redundant AUX_CLK± and REF_CLK±. As mentioned earlier, SpaceVPX uses four OpenVPX user defined pins on the P1 connector to define REF_CLK1± and REF_CLK2±. SpaceVPX Lite uses these to land the redundant AUX_CLK± and REF_CLK±. Consequently, SpaceVPX Lite supports full single string compatibility with OpenVPX. To achieve fully radial and redundant utility signals for OpenVPX as well, the user defined signals on P1, row g, wafers 7, 9, 11 and 13 must accept redundant AUX_CLK± and REF_CLK±.

Table 1. SpaceVPX Lite System Controllers Interoperate with OpenVPX Payload Modules

SpaceVPX Lite Designation	OpenVPX Compatible System Controller Profile
SYSRESET*	SYSRESET*
AUX_CLK±	AUX_CLK±
REF_CLK±	REF_CLK±
RAD1_USR	SM(0)
RAD2_USR	SM(1)
RAD3_USR	User Defined
RAD4_USR	User Defined

System Controller Profiles

SpaceVPX and SpaceVPX Lite adopt the slot and module profile definition scheme of OpenVPX. The Slot Profile identifies the type of signals used for each pin on the backplane connector. Each Module Profile identifies the specific signal for that type.

SpaceVPX Lite Slot Profiles

A SpaceVPX Lite System Controller includes all the interfaces necessary to directly control resets and clocks as well as provide control communications over the Control Plane. On the second connector (labeled P1) from the top of Figure 3, eight Data Plane ports map to eight Thin Pipes (TPs). A TP consists of four differential signals on two wafers. SpaceVPX and SpaceVPX Lite module profiles assign SpaceWire to these TPs. OpenVPX profiles typically use 1000BASE-T Ethernet on TPs. The bottom connector on the SpaceVPX Lite System Controller Slot Profile shows another eight TPs for Utility Management. The table on the upper right of Figure 3 breaks out the TP into specific signal types. The first three: SYSRESET*, AUX_CLK± and REF_CLK± are required utility signals for OpenVPX, SpaceVPX and now SpaceVPX Lite. The next four signals, RADn_USR are user defined and specified further by Module Profiles.

SpaceVPX Lite Module Profiles

The two tables in Figure 4 and Table 1 show three possible Module Profiles for the SpaceVPX Lite System Controller. The SpaceVPX and SpaceVPX Lite standards define these profiles in more detail, but these three tables show examples of how they define different sets of pins among the eight TPs on P1. Module Profiles identify all the interfaces selectable in the standard that fit into these TPs. Two possibilities include SpaceWire or 1000BASE-T Ethernet. The System Controller Module Profile shown in Figure 4 shows a different definition for the utility TPs depending on whether the System Controller interfaces with a payload module or a PowerSX. In this case, SpaceVPX system management over SM(3:0) provides the interface to the PowerSX. Yet, the PowerSX is a much simpler device than the SpaceUM, so a simpler interface may suffice. A System Controller supplier will likely use a field programmable gate array (FPGA) device for the utility TPs to enable support for a broad range of interface types on the RADn_USR pins.

Backplane Topologies

The SpaceVPX Systems Specification standard includes several backplane profiles showing usage of the slot profiles in a topology. These profiles show a

connection diagram of how all the signaling planes and power get routed into a topology. These signaling planes include the Control Plane, Data Plane, Expansion Plane, Management Plane and Utility Plane. In comparison, Figures 2, 4, 7 and 8 showed only utility plane connections where backplane profile BKP3-DIS12-15.2.9-n, shown in Figure 9, also shows the other signal planes. This profile shows a typical 3U SpaceVPX topology with a central switch connecting the Control Plane and a mesh connected Data Plane. For six payload slots and two controller slots, we need four SpaceUMs, two per slot. Backplane profiles do not need to support all planes. In this example, no Expansion Plane exists due to the limited number of pins available on a 3U module.

Figure 9. Typical SpaceVPX 3U Backplane Profile BKP3-DIS12-15.2.9-n Needs 4 SpaceUMs

SpaceVPXLite Backplane Profiles

Figure 10 shows a SpaceVPXLite equivalent topology to the one shown in Figure 9. In the SpaceVPXLite topology, the System Controller modules reside in slots 4 and 5 with the PowerSX in slot 9. The Utility Plane signals connect in the same way as the topology shown in Figure 8, but with the slots in a different order. A card slot arrangement such as shown in Figure 10 has advantages in cable routing and EMI control by bringing power in from

the right of the chassis then to the PowerSX before getting distributed to the digital slots. In comparison with Figure 9, the SpaceVPXLite topology achieves the same number of payload modules, but with a total compliment of three fewer modules overall to implement the topology.

Figure 10. SpaceVPXLite Equivalent Profile to BKP3-DIS12-15.2.9-n Needs Only One PowerSX

Backplane Routing Alternatives

Typical VPX and OpenVPX implementations use backplanes for connectivity, but recent developments may soon render backplanes obsolete. VPX emerged to provide a backplane connector and standard pinout to handle high speed serial interconnects up to 6.25 GBaud. Some companies report satisfactory results up to 10 GBaud with the same connectors [6]. However, with technology moving rates to 28 GBaud and beyond, “an important alternative technology for the future of high speed serial link backplanes is using cables” as cited by Dr. Eric Bogatin at DesignCon 2014[7].

Cabling from Rear Transition Modules

To stay alive and gain widespread adoption, a standard must accommodate advances in technology. VPX, and by way of inheritance OpenVPX and SpaceVPX, provides a convenient means to interconnect without relying on backplanes for connectivity. ANSI/VITA 46.10 “Rear Transition Module for VPX” defines a module and interconnections to attach directly to the backplane

edge connector [8]. This module converts signals, intended for backplane transmission, to instead drive/receive over coax cables or fiber-optics. Figure 11 shows how an RTM connects to a 6U SpaceVPX module. In addition to providing the necessary interface electronics, the RTM offers the connectors and I/O assignment to align with other standards such as the SpaceAGE Bus [9]. SpaceAGE uses frames instead of backplanes. A SpaceVPXLite 3U module with backplane and RTM all fit within the mechanical envelope of the SpaceAGE frame.

Figure 11. RTM Breaks-out SpaceVPXLite 3U Module I/O to Cable Connectors

Coax and Fiber-Optic Direct Attach Cabling

Two other alternatives to routing high speed serdes on the backplane include coax cabling with ANSI/VITA 67.x and fiber-optic cabling with ANSI/VITA 66.x [10, 11]. These two standards describe ways to include blindmate coax connectors, fiber-optic connectors or a combination of both into a VPX module. A 3U OpenVPX system using both standards has been proposed by Peddicord [12]. Recent activity by the OpenVPX Working Group also includes adding more of these types of profiles. Coax brings RF signals into the module using 67.x and serdes over fiberoptics per 66.x attaches it to high-speed communications by way of an external

network switch. Having these signals enter through the backplane side of the module typically simplifies cable routing in the host platform.

Platform Host Hook-Up

We have covered how SpaceVPXLite system components hook-up together, but eventually it needs to hook-up to a host of some type. SpaceVPXLite has the same interfaces as SpaceVPX for the hook-up to a platform controller.

Utility Signal Hook-Up to Host

Figure 12, shows pins on connector P0 assigned to REF_CLK±, AUX_CLK±, and SYSRESET* that also match with the VPX standard pin assignments. These pins connect to the platform to establish a master source for these signals. The platform also either drives the SYSCON* signal, along with parity signal SYSCONP*, to select the active System Controller or straps them with jumpers. A separate set of signals, called SYS_CON_SEL(2:0), go to the PowerSX to switch power on to the selected System Controller. If the platform needs to make cross-strapped connections, then a second set of REF_CLK±, AUX_CLK±, and SYSRESET* connect up to the REF_CLK1±, REF_CLK2± and MaskableReset*, respectively, in the same manner as utility signals connect from System Controller modules to payload modules. Finally, the POWER_SEL(2:0) signals go to the PowerSX to select which of the redundant power supply inputs to use to power all the modules. Separate from these power supply inputs, a persistent, low current source provides power to the PowerSX for the switches and system management control circuits.

Figure 12. System Controllers Have Their Own Utility Signal Pin Endpoints for Connecting to a Master Source of Clocks and Resets; Or, for Cascading from Other System Controller Modules

Control and Data Plane Hook-up to Host

Through these required interfaces, the platform host selects which input power supply to use and which System Controller to use, but control and data communications tend to be more application driven. SpaceVPX and SpaceVPXLite topologies, like OpenVPX topologies, include a few Control Plane and/or Data Plane interfaces for connection to the host. The SpaceVPX topology shown in Figure 9 and SpaceVPXLite topology shown in Figure 10 both have Control Plane TPs from redundant System Controllers available for communications with external equipment.

Unlimited Scalability

Up to this point we have only considered 3U topologies using redundant System Controllers capable of interfacing with up to eight modules. If you need to connect with nine or more modules SpaceVPXLite offers a convenient solution. As a

better alternative to abandoning 3U and going to 6U modules, SpaceVPXLite offers a means to stick with 3U and scale out as needed. 3U modules cool easier due to a shorter heat path from components to the rails and fit into more spaces. With about a third of the functionality in a 3U module compared to a 6U module, a finer grain m of n tends to yield more performance in a massively parallel and redundant system. Any system standard should provide the means to scale out as required to meet all the needs of the community it serves. SpaceVPXLite accomplishes unlimited scalability through the use of the utility pins on its P0/J0 connector. As shown in Figure 12, these pins connect to the host platform, or to another System Controller, for system clocks and resets. If using a topology such as the one shown in Figure 10, a System Controller for another set of modules occupies one of the payload slots. This System Controller then connects utility signals to another eight modules. The pattern continues down to several layers of hierarchy as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13. SpaceVPXLite Scales Out to Massively Parallel or Redundant Systems

Conclusion

SpaceVPXLite adds a viable low Size, Weight and Power alternative to SpaceVPX for 3U modules while maintaining all essential SpaceVPX capability. It offers a radial distribution alternative for OpenVPX and thus opens the high availability application space to the OpenVPX market place as well. The infinite scalability of SpaceVPXLite creates opportunities to rapidly develop and deploy large numbers of highly redundant high performance modules. These modules could be based on state-of-the-art technology in triple, quad or greater redundancy in high availability demanding applications. Or, more rugged modules could be deployed in dual or lower ratio m of n configurations to save on size, weight and cost.

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